

EDUCATING THE CHILDREN OF BONDED MIGRANT LABOURERS: STEPPING FOR ACHIEVING UEE

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ABSTRACT

Migration is an inevitable phenomenon in job seeking population. The migrant children of parents of low-wage earning move from one district to another district, or states, accompany their parents on a quest for seasonal employment are quite detached from education & victimized as educationally vulnerable. They are deprived of basic education and therefore mistreated by violation of fundamental right to receive education and child right.

The brickfields in West Bengal generally employ these migrant bonded workers. To earn livelihood, the workers arrive with their families from distant places – the adult couples working hard on the brickfield while their children are playing around or are also engaged by their parents. This has led to a lacuna in the achievement of functional UEE. Since the active season is from November to May, the families stay at work place for that period and go back to their native places for the remaining part of the year - making the educational condition of these children totally unstable. Most of them have never been to school. It has become extremely urgent to devise some mechanisms so that these children can be enrolled in schools and continue their education. The present researchers have tried to conceptualize the schemes, those intended to realize the UEE in case of these marginalized children. The full paper discusses on the conditions of education of children of migrant labourers, and the detail schemes and mechanisms for their education to eradicate illiteracy and achieve UEE.

KEYWORDS: Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) Bonded Migrant Labourer. Marginalized Children, and Education.

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